

Recent Research Accomplishments on the International Space Station

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Abstract--Astronauts have conducted more than four years of continuous space research aboard the International Space Station (ISS). The US Laboratory Module, *Destiny*, is outfitted with a robust suite of scientific equipment to support spaceflight research. Research, albeit limited, is ongoing in spite the grounding of the Space Shuttle fleet as a result of the loss of the *Columbia* in February 2003. Results from the last four years of research on ISS are now appearing in the scientific literature. Indeed, scientific articles are now being submitted to peer-reviewed journals from the ISS by the Science Officer on board.

This paper addresses the recent research results and accomplishments; and discusses the unique challenges faced in these early years of ISS assembly, including the methods for conduct of research while the Space Shuttle is unavailable as a resource for deploying and returning experiments for the ISS. We also discuss how the research portfolio is being realigned to support the use of ISS to enable NASA's Exploration Mission.¹

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1. THE CHALLENGES POSED FOR ISS RESEARCH BY THE GROUNDING OF THE SPACE SHUTTLE FLEET1**
- 2. MEETING THE CHALLENGES2**
- 3. RESEARCH RESULTS ROLL IN FROM ISS5**
- 4. NEW OBJECTIVES FOR ISS RESEARCH8**
- 5. RESEARCH PLANS FOR 20058**
- 6. ISS RESEARCH BEYOND 2005.....9**
- ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS9**
- REFERENCES9**

1. THE CHALLENGES POSED FOR ISS RESEARCH BY THE GROUNDING OF THE SPACE SHUTTLE FLEET

Grounding of Space Shuttles following the *Columbia* accident on February 1, 2003 necessitated a different, and previously unanticipated, approach to execution of research on the International Space Station. Lack of Shuttle servicing for the ISS severely limits the mass that can be

brought to orbit, reduces the crew to two people rather than the planned three, and virtually eliminates the ability to return research samples. Rhatigan [1] describes the immediate re-planning that took place after the accident that accommodated changes in launch schedules and on-orbit crew time availability during the ISS Expedition 6.

Mass to/from the ISS

Up-mass (mass of experiment equipment and samples to be brought to ISS) and down-mass (mass of equipment and samples to be brought back to Earth) have been even more limited than was originally expected when post-*Columbia* replanning began. Table 1 shows the total mass brought to/from the ISS for NASA research purposes since the *Columbia* accident using the Russian Progress logistics vehicle and the Soyuz crewed vehicle. Upmass on Progress vehicles has totaled 34 kg to date and 17 kg on Soyuz vehicles, while downmass on Soyuz has been 6.2 kg through October 2004. This is in contrast to the nearly 6500 kg of research mass brought to the ISS between late 2000 and December 2002 via the Space Shuttle (and analogous down-mass during that period, such that there was no prior back log).

Table 1. Up-mass and Down-mass for U.S. Research on ISS since Grounding of the Space Shuttle

Vehicle	Launch	Upmass (kg)	Landing	Down- mass (kg)
<i>Progress:</i>				
12 P	Aug 2003	15		
13 P	Jan 2004	13		
14 P	May 2004	0		
15 P	Aug 2004	0		
16 P	Dec 2004	6		
<i>Soyuz:</i>				
5 S			Apr 2003	5.6
6 S	Apr 2003	1	Oct 2003	0
7 S	Oct 2003	16	Apr 2004	0.55
8 S	Apr 2004	0	Oct 2004	0
9 S	Oct 2004	0		0

¹ U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright. IEEEAC 2005 paper #310, Version 1, updated Oct. 20, 2004.

Currently, a number of experiments completed on orbit have samples or data on recorded media that await return. Some experiment samples had a shelf-life that expired, and their science value has been compromised or lost.

Crew-time

Crew time has always been one of the most significant factors limiting the amount of research that can be done on ISS. Research crew time is highly variable during ISS construction due to the realities of daily maintenance of the on-orbit outpost. Additional EVAs (extra-vehicular activities, i.e., spacewalks), unplanned equipment outages, and rescheduling of visiting vehicles all contribute to a dynamic research operations environment. Somewhat mitigating this, a ‘job jar’ approach to payload operations has evolved to take advantage of free moments of crew time. Also, we now have the flexibility (in contrast to short-duration experiments conducted on the Space Shuttle) to extend the planned duration of an experiment on ISS to complete the investigations’ objectives when crew time is temporarily limited—this approach has been utilized a number of times.

The lack of Shuttle servicing to ISS (and commensurate reduction in re-supply of critical needs such as food, air, and water) reduced the crew size to two people, rather than three; but with ISS construction halted, it was expected that a larger percentage of crew time would be available for research [1]. However, with the absence of Shuttle flights to bring up spares and logistics, on-orbit troubleshooting of malfunctions in critical items such as EVA suits and oxygen generation equipment has taken more crew time than originally expected. The three crews (of three people) on ISS just prior to grounding of the Shuttle (Expeditions 4, 5, and 6) spent 15.2, 13.6 and 14.7 hours/week on research operations, respectively. In contrast, the three crews (of two people) that followed (Expeditions 7, 8, and 9) spent 6.7, 9.5 and 8.2 hours/week on research, respectively. Thus, there has been a significant reduction in the already limited time for the crew to complete research activities, but it should be noted that per-capita average time per week has been slightly higher.

Baseline Data Collection

Another challenge without the Shuttle flying is ensuring baseline data collection (BDC) for human life science research before launch and immediately after landing. Many of the physiological changes that interest investigators happen during the first few hours of microgravity and during the first few hours upon landing on Earth. When the Shuttle lands at Kennedy Space Center, there is a dedicated Baseline Data Collection Facility where astronauts spend their first hours back on Earth participating in medical examinations and human life science investigations. With a Soyuz landing in Kazakhstan, it can be a few hours before the crew is located and 12 hours or more before they arrive back in Star City, Russia where BDC can commence. The

investigations that absolutely require BDC within a few days of launch and/or the first few hours of landing have had to delay operations until the Shuttle resumes flying so as not to compromise data integrity. For other experiments, investigators have proceeded at risk and modified their protocols to accommodate these changed landings and the associated post-landing planned events. In all cases, modifications required compromise to less than ideal data collection scenarios in method, timing, or both. It is not known at this time whether these modifications will affect data integrity and/or the investigator’s abilities to achieve conclusive results.

2. MEETING THE CHALLENGES

The plan for the Space Shuttle return-to-flight has matured since the publication of Ref. 1, and as a result, a broader interim research strategy was evolved through the collaborative efforts of the ISS Program Scientist, Increment Scientists, Science Officers on board the ISS, and the research community. The interim research strategy has focused on five primary methods of optimizing research return.

1. Complete experiments already on ISS.

Given that some experiments were on ISS prior to the *Columbia* accident and could be completed with available crew time, this was the most obvious strategy. In some cases, materials had been pre-positioned for future data collections/experiments. An interesting example involved an on-going study called “Foot/Ground Reaction Forces during Space Flight” (FOOT, Peter Cavanaugh, The Cleveland Clinic Foundation). This experiment compares daily mechanical loads in the joints of the lower extremities on Earth and ISS [2]. This mechanical loading may be an important factor determining loss of bone mass and muscle strength during long stays in microgravity. To obtain the necessary data for this experiment, a pair of instrumented exercise pants (the Lower Extremity Monitoring Suit) are custom fit to each participating crewmember. Science Officer Mike Foale (Figure 1) used an onboard sewing kit to modify the fit of pants that had been pre-positioned on ISS for someone else, and was able to participate fully in the experiment, “saving” a full increment of data and one subject that would have been otherwise lost.

The approach of completing experiments already on orbit was limited for some experiments by the lack of ability to return experiment samples before their expiration. “Coarsening in Solid-Liquid Mixtures” (CSLM-2, Peter Voorhees, Northwestern University) investigated the kinetics of competitive particle growth (coarsening) within a liquid lead/tin matrix. Samples from this experiment were not returned to Earth in time for evaluating the results. Although the data was lost, useful engineering data was collected on equipment function.

2. Perform additional experiments on reusable samples.

Several experiments on board ISS had samples that could be re-used or re-tested beyond the original experiment design. The experiment titled “Toward Understanding Pore Formation and Mobility during Controlled Directional Solidification in a Microgravity Environment” (PFMI, Richard Grugel, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center), looked at melting and solidification in a microgravity environment to improve the manufacturing and casting of different materials. The data on solidification came from video images of bubbles as in Figure 2, and the experiment was expanded beyond the original test plan by melting and re-solidifying the samples with different processing parameters (temperature gradients and solidification rates).

Figure 1 – Expedition 8 Commander and NASA Science Officer Mike Foale wears the customized Lower Extremity Monitoring Suit and balances on the footplate of a special track attached to the Human Research Facility rack in the *Destiny* U.S. Laboratory to perform electromyography calibration operations as part of the Foot/Ground Reaction Forces during Spaceflight Experiment (ISS008E20918).

Similarly, the colloidal materials for the experiment “Investigating the Structure of Paramagnetic Aggregates from Colloidal Emulsions” (InSPACE, Alice P. Gast, Massachusetts Institute of Technology), examining the

properties of fluids with and without a magnetic field, were perfectly reusable and the test plan was expanded to incorporate additional test conditions. The additional runs have not been completed to date, but are being held as a reserve activity, should crew time become available.

Figure 2 – Image of the solid liquid interface of the Pore Formation and Mobility (PFMI) experiment. Bubbles detach from the interface and move up the temperature gradient (right to left), courtesy of Dr. Richard Grugel, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center.

3. Develop and “fast track” new small experiments to fly on Progress vehicles.

Investigators showed real ingenuity in developing new, small experiments that could be prepared quickly and sent up to ISS on one of the Russian Progress re-supply flights (on a non-interference basis with crew and vehicle survival items). In the physical sciences, these “fast track” experiments included studies of capillary flow, bulk metallic glasses, properties of fluids, and supercritical fluids, all sent up on Progress flight 13P (Table 1). The results of one of these fast track experiments “Phase Separation near the Critical Point in Microgravity” are summarized in section 3, below.

As another example, in the “Viscous Liquid Foam - Bulk Metallic Glass” experiment (William Johnson, and Chris Veazey, California Institute of Technology), a soldering iron was used to heat ampoules filled with bulk metallic glass and a gas to cause them to foam. The cooled samples of foam structure are awaiting return to Earth. Samples of “bubbloy” (for bubble-alloy) made on Earth [3] have great potential for applications like crumple zones of automobiles and were voted “Best of What’s Next 2004” by Popular Science [4]. These materials are strong and lightweight, making them excellent candidate materials for use in future spacecraft. Since the physics of bubble and foam formation is different in microgravity, results of the “Foam” experiment will help both in understanding the foaming process and designing better versions of these new materials.

The “Advanced Diagnostic Ultrasound in Microgravity” (ADUM, Scott A. Dulchavsky, Henry Ford Health System) experiment was accelerated from a planned later deployment since it involved very little up-mass. This experiment develops on-orbit ultrasound proficiency training in order to expand telemedicine capabilities. Crewmembers learn to perform the ultrasound scans on each other while being guided remotely by experienced operators on the ground. A computer-based training tool, the Onboard Proficiency Enhancer (OPE) was sent to orbit on compact disk (Figure 3). Crewmembers then used the existing onboard ultrasound capability to image leg bone (to assess bone loss indicators), and thoracic (heart and lung) and abdominal organs (Figure 4).

Figure 3 – Example of interactive training for the Advanced Ultrasound experiment using the Onboard Proficiency Enhancer (OPE, courtesy of Shannon Melton, NASA Johnson Space Center)

Figure 4 – As part of the Advanced Ultrasound experiment, Mike Fincke performs an ultrasound on orbit, guided by experts on the ground (ISS009E07816).

ADUM investigators also evaluated the ability of crewmembers to perform new imaging that might be

unexpectedly required (as in the case of an injury) using the shoulder as an example [5]. The crew had received 2.5 hours of ultrasound training several months before the flight and a 1-hour OPE review on orbit, but no specific training in shoulder anatomy or shoulder ultrasound techniques. The real-time ultrasound video of the shoulder was transmitted to remote experts at the Johnson Space Center who verbally guided the astronaut performing the sonography (Figure 4).

The video images were of excellent quality and allowed evaluation of shoulder integrity. New data on ultrasound imaging of organs and systems in microgravity becomes an important foundation for ultrasound diagnostics now and in future exploration missions. A summary of these results was submitted for publication from orbit by Science Officer Mike Fincke [5].

4. Develop new experiments requiring no upmass.

Novel experiments were designed that made use of materials already on ISS. Experiments with “household” materials like water, honey, and silicon oil were used to address some of the unanswered questions in the physics of fluid behavior in microgravity. “Miscible Fluids in Microgravity” (MFMG, John Pojman, University of Southern Mississippi) and “Fluid Merging Viscosity Measurement” (FMVM, Edwin Ethridge, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center) examined the properties of mixing fluids and fluid viscosity, respectively, using these simple materials.

Figure 5 – Soldering for the In Space Soldering Investigation (ISSI) during Expedition 9. The yellow area is a ball of flux on the surface of the molten solder.

The “In Space Soldering Investigation” (ISSI, Richard Grugel, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center) includes a series of test cases using soldering materials on orbit. Expedition 7 and 8 crewmembers prepared the soldering experiment, and the soldering was carried out on Expeditions 9 and 10. The precise angle at which the solder meets the wire is driven by forces such as surface tension, gravity, and wetting of the wire. Removing the effects of gravity lets physicists better understand these other influences. Soldered materials are now awaiting return to Earth (Figure 5). Review of the experiment videotapes revealed melting kinetics, wetting characteristics, and equilibrium shape attainment of the solder charge. Additionally, the accumulated liquid flux was observed to

rapidly and circumferentially translate over the surface of the molten solder ball, an unexpected phenomenon that is currently being assessed. Evaluation of the experimental results is expected to promote our knowledge of fabrication and repair techniques that might be employed during extended space exploration missions.

5. Maximize international cooperation.

As the ISS is and international endeavor, collaborations with the ISS International Partner space agencies have also facilitated increased research return. For example, the Grenada Crystallization Facility (GCF) featured samples prepared by international scientists (led by Hiroaki Tanaka, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency), in hardware built in Spain for the European Space Agency (ESA), taken to orbit on a Russian vehicle, transferred on the ISS into U.S. hardware (the Commercial Generic Bioprocessing Apparatus, CGBA, to provide thermal conditioning), and later returned on a Russian vehicle [6]. Other examples of international cooperation in sharing experiments, transportation and hardware during this period are PROMISS (Protein Microscope for International Space Station) and the Hand Posture Analyzer (HPA) [7]. Technical difficulties prevented completion of the Heat experiment (J.C. Legros Euro Heat Pipes S.A., Belgium) during the Dutch Soyuz *Delta* mission in April 2004. This European Space Agency experiment studying heat transfer performance of grooved heat pipes for cooling in microgravity was later completed by Mike Fincke on Expedition 9, with all objectives from the original Soyuz mission completed.

Figure 6 – Expedition 8 Commander and Science Officer Michael Foale and ESA astronaut and *Delta* Taxi Flight (Soyuz 8S) visiting crewmember André Kuipers work at the Microgravity Sciences Glovebox (MSG) in the *Destiny* U.S. Laboratory (ISS008E21999).

In summary, the five research strategies discussed above have served us well in continuing a limited research program aboard the ISS during Expeditions 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, while the space shuttle has been unavailable. Under the circumstances of such limited resources, the continuation of research activity on ISS was not assured and is itself a significant achievement.

The NASA Science Officer

Beginning with Expedition 5, NASA started a new emphasis on science activities by designating Dr. Peggy Whitson as the NASA Science Officer on-board the ISS. NASA has continued naming a Science Officer for each Expedition, and this has served well during Shuttle downtime. The empowerment of an astronaut in completing science objectives has increased the interchange between crew on orbit and researchers on the ground. Earlier in the ISS Program, the dialogue between crew and Principal Investigators had not been emphasized. The ISS Program Scientist has worked in collaboration with Science Officers on ISS to increase the dialogue prior to, during, and after the conduct of an experiment so that adjustments can be made as necessary to the test plan in a timeframe closer to real-time. During Expedition 8 (20 October 2003–26 April 2004), eight crew science-related conferences were held. During Expedition 9 (26 April–23 October 2004), 19 crew science-related conferences were conducted.

The interactions have increased as both the crew and researchers on the ground have found that results are better and tasks are completed more easily when there is improved communication. The more that dialog between scientist on orbit and scientists on the ground approaches similar scientific exchanges that routinely take place in a laboratory setting, the more productive the research on ISS can be. The intent is to improve this to the point where continuous adjustments to the originally planned procedures can be made as dictated by results.

Another dividend from the naming of a Science Officer has been the choices made by science officers to complete additional science activities during personal time on evenings and rest days. This volunteer time was originally called “Saturday Science” as a legacy from the efforts that Don Pettit made during Expedition 6 to use his free time on Saturdays to develop educational materials [8]. Mike Fincke of Expedition 9 had a personal goal of completing additional research objectives during his free time and used the Saturday Science as a structure for requesting ground support in completing additional research tasks.

A preliminary estimate is that 40% of the U.S. research completed during Expedition 9 was completed during off-duty hours. Many of the experiments described in this article (including FMVM, Heat, ISSI, and MFMG already discussed, and BCAT-3 discussed in section 3), and conferences with investigators were completed during this volunteer time. For this dedication to U.S. research, Fincke received a commendation from the NASA Space Station Utilization Advisory Subcommittee (SSUAS) of the Biological and Physical Research Advisory Committee, a standing committee of the NASA Advisory Council.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS ROLL IN FROM ISS

In spite of all the difficulties the research community has

faced during the initial assembly of the ISS and the Shuttle down-time, we are gratified to report that research results are now rolling in from the ISS. This section provides highlights from the more than 80 U.S.-sponsored on-orbit research, educational, commercial and technology-demonstration investigations either completed or underway. A summary of major publications or research results from ISS is compiled in Table 2. In keeping with the concept of ISS crewmembers as participating scientists, two publications have now been submitted from orbit. The first, submitted by Michael Foale is in review, the second, submitted by Mike Fincke is accepted in the journal *Radiology* [5].

We highlight some examples of the most recent results in this section, emphasizing novel results and projects not yet included in Table 2.

Table 2. Published Research Results from ISS (including experiments conducted onboard, and sortie experiments conducted on Space Shuttle flights to and from ISS).

Topics	References
Life Sciences:	
Radiation	9, 10
Bone, Muscle, Kinematics	2, 7, 11, 12
Immune Function	13, 14
Neurovestibular System	15, 16, 17, 18, 19
Clinical Space Medicine	5
Animal Husbandry	20
Plant Culture	21, 22, 23
Physical Sciences:	
Crystal Growth	24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31
Materials Processing	32, 33
Colloid Physics	34
Earth Observations	35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41
Space Operations:	
Vibrations & Isolation	42, 43, 44, 45
Microgravity Environment	46

Effects of EVA and Long-Term Exposure to Microgravity on Pulmonary Function (PuFF) (John B. West, University of California, San Diego)

This investigation, which was manifested on four ISS Expeditions, investigates questions on how the pulmonary system is affected by long-term spaceflight and Extravehicular Activities (EVAs). Over a long-term flight, there is possible exposure to noxious gases or particulate matter in the closed atmosphere of the ISS. EVAs, like reverse-pressure deep water dives, involve significant changes in pressure and composition of air breathed by the astronauts, which might significantly affect lung function. To examine these effects, long duration crewmembers conducted a battery of non-invasive tests of pulmonary function (Figure 7) to assess whether changes occur in the pulmonary vasculature over the course of a stay on ISS with multiple EVAs [47]. Because of mission requirements, data

collections immediately following EVAs were not possible, so it remains unknown whether there are significant pulmonary function changes post-EVA. The data does suggest, however, that the de-nitrogenation (i.e., pre-breathing) protocols currently in use on ISS result in no lasting adverse effects on lung function [48].

Figure 7 - Expedition 6 Astronaut Don Pettit sets up the PuFF hardware next to the Human Research Facility Rack (ISS006E07133).

Sub-Regional Assessment of Bone Loss in the Axial Skeleton in Long-Term Spaceflight (Thomas F. Lang, University of California, San Francisco).

The objective of this study was to determine the distribution of bone loss in the spine and hip in long-duration spaceflight using quantitative computed tomography (QCT) and to assess how bone is recovered after return. One of the first Bioastronautics research investigations to begin on ISS, this study recruited 14 subjects between Expedition 2 through Expedition 8. At least 8 subjects have been back long enough for Lang to have also measured their bone density one year post flight [49] to assess recovery. On ISS, average bone mineral density is lost at an average rate of about 0.9% per month in the lumbar spine and 1.4% per month in the femoral neck [12]. For comparison, a post-menopausal woman experiences losses of bone mineral on the order of 1% per year (e.g., [50]). The study has also shown regions of greatest bone mass loss during a mission and different rates of loss in different parts of the bone [12]. For example, in the hip, losses of mass in the cortical bone (the outer part of the bone) averaged around 0.5%/month whereas losses in the trabecular bone (the inner parts of the bone) averaged 2.5%/month [12]. In the past, bone loss was only measured by dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) which underestimates bone loss as it only provides a composite measurement of the bone compartments. These new findings more accurately demonstrate the risk of bone fracture for astronauts assigned to long duration missions upon their return to Earth (or another planetary gravity field).

Physics of Colloids in Space (PCS) (David A. Weitz, Harvard University).

Several investigations on ISS have used colloid mixtures to study physical processes. In the first of these, light scattering was used to measure the limitations of how colloids aggregate. The compositions of the colloid solutions were controlled to get behavior similar to pure liquids, gels or crystals. On Earth, gravity limits the maximum cluster size of the colloid due to sedimentation. In microgravity, however, thermally induced strains limit the cluster size of colloidal aggregates and determine the lowest volume fraction that will gel [34].

Binary Colloidal Alloy Test (BCAT-3) (David A. Weitz and Peter J. Lu, Harvard University, Arjun Yodh and Jian Zhang, University of Pennsylvania).

Building on the experience from PCS, this investigation utilized the unique environment provided by microgravity and colloids as a model system for exploring the physical behavior of molecules. The same physical processes that affect the properties of molecules occur in colloids in space, but unlike molecules, the colloids are large enough to observe directly and slow enough to reveal how the system evolves. The colloids used are submicroscopic spheres of Plexiglas (a thousand times smaller than the width of a human hair) and polymers (strings or coils) suspended in a fluid. BCAT-3 includes multiple sample chambers to evaluate two types of physical processes in colloids, the formation of crystals within them and their behavior as supercritical fluids. The chambers are mixed and then digitally photographed over time to observe changes (Figure 8). This investigation was begun during Expedition 8 and continued on Expedition 9 during Saturday Science (see Section 2) sessions that also allowed for a unique dialogue between crewmember and the investigators.

The samples for studying surface crystallization were selected by Arjun Yodh and Jian Zhang at the University of Pennsylvania. Theory predicts a larger particle can be trapped against a surface (like the wall of a container) by the motion of the little particles. Eventually enough larger particles should be trapped to start forming a solid crystal. However, this theory cannot be confirmed on Earth because gravity leads to sedimentation and convection. In over two months on orbit, one of the samples began to show crystals forming on the edge of the container.

Scientists on the ground requested that the experiment be lengthened to see whether the sample would continue to crystallize and whether their other samples would begin to form visible crystals. Astronaut Mike Fincke requested an air-to-ground conference to talk with the investigators about the next steps for the experiment. These BCAT-3 surface crystallization samples do not crystallize on Earth, and now that they have grown in microgravity, the existing theory will have to be modified to reflect new observations of the timescale for crystal growth.

In the samples for studying supercritical fluids, selected by David Weitz and Peter Lu at Harvard University, colloid-polymer mixtures in different concentrations are allowed to separate over time. In gravity, the denser component of the mixture would eventually settle to the bottom. In orbit, however, the phase separation gradually forms "clumps" of colloid dense areas throughout the mixture (Figure 9). Over time (noted in figure) the dense areas interact and become larger. This serves as a model for the behavior of supercritical fluids (a state of matter that has properties of gases and liquids), used for everything from decaffeinating coffee to making pharmaceuticals. So a better understanding of their properties had important implications on the ground.

Figure 8 - Expedition 8 Commander and Science Officer Michael Foale uses the digital still camera to photograph samples for the Binary Colloidal Alloy Test -3 (BCAT-3) experiment (ISS009E20610).

The seven critical point samples have provided a dynamic set of photographs showing at what concentrations the Investigators' colloidal-polymer samples will separate into two components (Figure 9). This is analogous to the separation of samples on Earth into liquid and gas phases, which are indistinguishable (do not separate) at or above a critical point. Detailed analysis of the data is ongoing.

Figure 9 – Separation of the critical point samples as part of the BCAT-3 experiment [51] (courtesy of Peter Lu, Harvard University).

Crew Earth Observations (CEO) (Kamlesh Lulla, NASA Johnson Space Center).

Innovation in photographic technique has provided unique observations of the Earth obtainable only from the International Space Station. Astronauts are photographing the Earth in support of scientific investigations and are provided with daily targets of opportunity to track long-term planetary changes as well as single events in dynamic regions on Earth. One early unanticipated result from the Crew Earth Observations (CEO) payload was the ability that astronauts develop over longer durations in orbit to track the motion of the earth underneath them and capture extremely sharp photographs with high-magnification lenses. They do this by getting the immediate feedback from a digital camera to improve their motion tracking skills. Using the highest magnification lens combination on board the ISS (800mm), the astronauts routinely achieve a resolution of 6 meters using commercial-grade digital cameras. This was documented in the first publication of ISS research results [35].

Expedition 6 Science Officer Don Pettit took this innovation one step further by building a “barn door tracker” that improved motion tracking sufficiently to get clear long-exposure night shots of Earth (Figure 10). These shots represent the only high spatial resolution data on city lights available [40].

Figure 10 – Night view of London taken from the ISS using the barn door tracker on February 4, 2003 (ISS006E22939).

4. NEW OBJECTIVES FOR ISS RESEARCH

One of the most significant events in the history of the ISS for the U.S. occurred on January 14, 2004 when President George W. Bush announced the *Vision for Space Exploration* [52]. The vision recognized that “Research aboard the International Space Station and at various laboratories on Earth is critical to understanding the effects of space environments on the human body, developing techniques for mitigating these hazards, minimizing the logistical burden of supporting humans far from Earth, and addressing remote medical emergencies.” This vision

redirected the focus of research on the ISS from being a world class scientific laboratory to a goal that “Space Station research necessary to support human explorers on other worlds will be complete by 2016” [52:15]. Subsequently, the *Exploration Systems Interim Strategy* has identified that the ISS should “reemerge as a platform for conducting experiments relating to human health and performance and the development and testing of life support technologies” (53:57).

NASA is currently in the process of transforming its organization and building a new strategy for the utilization of ISS to match these new objectives. We plan to address this approach in a future publication [54], due to both length constraints herein and the timing of anticipated decisions within NASA. Reference [54] will include our current understanding of the major exploration mission risks that the ISS can be used to address and current progress in realigning NASA’s research portfolio for ISS to support exploration missions. We will discuss the results of NASA’s efforts over the past year to realign the ISS research programs to a product-driven portfolio that is targeted towards reducing the major risks of exploration oriented spaceflight. We will address how NASA intends to broaden the approach for selecting the best investigations for ISS that will enable the exploration missions. We will also discuss how targeted technological developments can enable mission design trade studies. The interchange between mission design and research needs is dynamic, where design decisions influence the type of research needed, and results of research influence design decisions.

5. RESEARCH PLANS FOR 2005

This year promises the Return-to-Flight of the Space Shuttle (scheduled in mid-2005), which should alleviate many of the pressures discussed in section 1. Though the first few flights will be primarily dedicated to testing out new Shuttle safety capabilities and addressing the maintenance back-log for the ISS, we will also see expanded research focused on exploration information needs as well as four new rack-level research facilities will be added to the *Destiny* laboratory module on ISS.

Until the Shuttle returns to flight and until strategic planning is complete, a process of triage is being used to prioritize the ISS research that is most relevant and timely for NASA’s Exploration mission. In this way the very precious resources of up-mass, crew time, on-orbit stowage, and down-mass are already being focused on exploration research. For early 2005, a small number of exploration related experiments are planned for transport to station via Progress vehicles. The first two Shuttle Missions after return to flight will be test flights of new safety protocols, and research up-mass and crew time on these flights remains extremely limited. The first significant research resources will be on mission ULF1.1 (STS-121), and significant research hardware will be delivered to ISS on the first flight

of the European Space Agency's Automated Transfer Vehicle (ATV), and on mission 12A.1 (STS-116).

The first of the rack facilities to deploy in 2005 will be the second Human Research Facility Rack (HRF2). This rack will add a body mass measurement device, and upgraded computer workstation, a refrigerated centrifuge and a Pulmonary Function System to the capabilities already on orbit [55]. Later in 2005 will see the deployment of SpaceDRUMS (Dynamically Responding Ultrasonic Matrix System), a material processing facility; the European Modular Cultivation System (EMCS); and the Minus Eighty Laboratory Freezer for ISS (MELFI). The MELFI will provide the ISS with a large volume (300 liters), low temperature (-80 to +4 degrees Celsius) freezer facility [56]. The EMCS, developed by ESA, provides a facility for variable gravity studies of plants, insects, amphibians, cell and tissue cultures. The first experiment to test the new hardware will look at plant growth. SpaceDRUMS has been designed to process materials of commercial size and quantity without the use of containers. These four facilities will greatly increase the types of experiments possible on the ISS.

6. ISS RESEARCH BEYOND 2005

Beyond 2005, strategic planning for research will be tightly tied to the developing requirements for exploration missions. A particular challenge is that many of the most important experiments require human subjects, or use animal models, both of which can require activities by the Shuttle crews on the way to ISS. Crew time to complete experiments during Shuttle missions is extremely limited, first by the demands of Shuttle Return-to-Flight activities, and later by the ISS construction activities (such as extravehicular activity and power system reconfiguration) scheduled for the near-term flights. Once assembly is complete, the planned retirement of the Space Shuttle and the capabilities of vehicles used to replace it will also affect the types of experiments that can be conducted.

Critical factors determining the numbers of human subjects available are the number of ISS crew members in residence, and the duration of each mission. The shift back to a crew of three when the Shuttle returns to flight, and the schedule for moving to a full crew complement of six (as life support capabilities of ISS are increased) are important milestones for obtaining sufficient human subjects and sufficient on-orbit research time.

Mission duration is also important. The nominal mission duration of 120-days is the optimal length for most human life science experiments, allowing sufficient time for long-duration effects to manifest and stabilize into predictable patterns. Shorter missions than the most recent 6-month stays will provide significantly more human subjects over the life of the ISS. 120-day missions have been recommended by all of the advisory organizations overseeing ISS research. Sufficient human subjects are

needed in order to ensure timely completion of research needed to define future exploration missions to the Moon and Mars [57]. Strategic planning in progress will also focus the set of research questions and approaches and optimize the numbers of human subjects needed on ISS. This is an important part of research redirection to align with the *Vision for Space Exploration*.

NASA is in the process of re-planning some of the ISS assembly sequence in order to accelerate advanced life support capability and optimize installation of various modules. The re-planning will affect the timing of the availability of research facilities, the number of crewmembers, and the availability of crew time. During 2006 and 2007, the plans are to complete a large portion of the outfitting of major facilities, with the timing of specific facilities still under review. Of particular interest to the science community will be the final schedule for deployment of research modules sponsored by the European Space Agency and Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency.

We refer those interested in future developments of the ISS research strategy to our next planned publication [54].

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